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CHESS
SET UP

Deliverable 7.8

Report on the events participated

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1. Introduction: Events' Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The Communication and Dissemination Plan of CHESSE SETUP Project (D7.1 Detailed Communication and Dissemination Plan) presented various strategic objectives (Figure 1). Among others, interact with other relevant European and National projects in creation of dissemination events, ensure synergies with other European strategies and encourage the roll-out of the solution among private companies and cities and regions across Europe.

*Figure 1. Strategic objectives of communication and dissemination.
(Source: D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, CHESSE SETUP Project)*

Therefore, with the aim to reach these goals and our targeted audience (Figure 2), two communication channels were essential as stated in Deliverable 7.1:

- **Clustering activities:** The dissemination plan aimed to raise awareness concerning the CHESSE SETUP's ecosystem, but also to enter CHESSE SETUP as a component of this ecosystem. Thus, **clustering activities** were a central part of the dissemination plan. Clustering activities covered workshops' organization, participation in expositions, congress and conferences, or all events gathering potential stakeholders. CHESSE SETUP's presence could be in form of a presentation/talk or to have a stand.
- **One-to-one communication, and local events.** The dissemination plan also allowed and considered other types of communication, at a smaller scale. Depending on the implementation results, and the exchanges between CHESSE

SETUP and the stakeholders, as well as the other CHESSE SETUP's members spent time with potential stakeholders in order to explain the implementation.

Figure 2. Stakeholders and target groups for communication and dissemination. (Source: D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, CHESSE SETUP Project).

The events organized or participated has been communicated and promoted through the **social media channels and the project website**, depending on their openness to the public.

This **Report on the Events Participated** covers both communication channels and present the activities organized in **two levels** and **chronologically** exposed:

Organization of specific events for the project

- Kick-off meeting and Final Conference
- Webinars or specific sessions
- Local take-up events or one to one communication meetings for the dissemination of CHESSE SETUP solution and project

Participation in third parties' events

- Participation in exhibitions, conferences, congresses or other events gathering potential stakeholders, or other European initiatives to ensure synergies

Annexes

- Other relevant Communication and Dissemination Activities by CHESSE SETUP
- Full list and information of events participated by partner Wansdronk
- Letters of interest
- Visual Thinking summary

2. Organization of specific events for the project

CHESSE SETUP Consortium, with direct support and coordination of WP7 leaders (EDN), organized specific events for the project. The aim of these specific events was to stimulate EU-wide networking and dissemination of project results.

It is interesting to note that CHESSE-SETUP communication and dissemination events are accompanied with parallel actions, by contacting attendants before or after the event, such as personal calls, mailings, and meetings, if needed.

2.1 Kick-off Meeting

On July 6th and 7th 2016 was held CHESSE SETUP's kick off meeting in Barcelona (Spain).

Each partner was represented, and all the representatives had a speech in order to introduce its company. Then, an overview of CHESSE SETUP was given by the lead partner BCN Ecologia. Each Work Package leader explained briefly the content of its missions, and its objectives.

Chess Setup team was given the opportunity to meet up, and to start a five-year long successful cooperation.

2.2 Final Conference

On September 18th 2020, a 2-hours virtual Final Conference for the project was organized. The plan was to held a physical final conference meeting, but due to worldwide COVID19 pandemic situation this plan was suspended and the Consortium opted finally for an online conference/live webinar. The platform used was Zoom and it was also live-streamed in YouTube, both allowing written interaction (chat) between the organizers, speakers and participants.

The Final Conference presented the results of the project for all the participants, targeted to the stakeholders and groups defined in the CHESSE SETUP Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.1) and database (D6.3). Therefore, the audience included potential users of the system and services such as buildings and energy sector professionals, key decision-makers in the construction sector both for private groups and public administrations, and private users interested in the system.

The message spread to disseminate the Final Conference through the different CHESSE SETUP communication channels was the following:

"In this online conference you will learn about the outcomes of the project, the key exploitation results and the transferability of the system towards Nearly Zero Energy Buildings with its innovative approach to thermal energy storage, energy efficiency and self-sufficiency, including a final Q/A debate session".

The communication channels used to disseminate it are as follows:

- CHESSETUP website
- Social Media (Twitter and LinkedIn)
- CHESSETUP last Press Release and Newsletter
- [BUILD UP](#), the European portal for energy efficient in buildings with a large stakeholder community.
- [European Commission Events/Calendar](#).
- [Agenda EU](#) platform, informing about events in EU, organizing them in different topics and shared interests.
- [Construction21 Agenda](#), a social media dedicated to all professionals active in the building and city sectors and interested in sustainability.
- [Email campaign](#) to our newsletter and website subscribers and CHESSETUP stakeholders' database and voice-to-voice to interested parties. The partners also collaborated by mailing through its distribution list and contacts.

Figure 3. Agenda and event dissemination of the Final Conference. (Source: Own elaboration)

The Final Conference was organized with the aim to give an active role to every partner and expose their different works, results and lessons learnt during the project. Furthermore, a special participant was invited to provide insight of the transferability and adoption of the system to other cases. Additionally, the collaboration of enterprises and cases that have expressed interest in CHESSETUP solution (via Abora Solar. The conference program was planned as follows (Table 1):

Time (CET)	Content	Speaker
11:00h	Welcome and Opening (with CHESSE SETUP Final Video premiere)	Lucia González, CEO of Edenway SL
11:10h	CHESSE SETUP System – an overview	Renee Wandsronk, Founder and Architect in Wandsronk Architecktuur
11:20h	New advancements in heat pumps implementation	Neil Hewitt, Director of Centre for Sustainable Technologies and Energy Professor in Ulster University
11:30h	Pilot experiences – 3 field studies	
	Lavola Pilot	Cristina Bayés, Energy Manager in Lavola Anthesis
	Sant Cugat Pilot	Gerard Riba, Head of Urban Maintenance in Sant Cugat
	Corby Pilot	Nick Bolton, Founder and Project Manager in Electric Corby
12:00h	Capitalization of CHESSE SETUP solution: impact, transferability and contributions towards NZEB	
	Control and Monitoring System	Jordi Ferrer, I+D & IT Manager in Wattia Innova
	Simulator System	Sergio Sánchez, Energy Coordinator in BcnEcologia
	CHESSE SETUP Services - ESCO	Josep Mitats, Project Engineer in Veolia
	Transferability and adoption to other cases (linking it with next section)	Special collaborator: Alejandro del Amo, CEO of Abora Solar
12:30h	Challenges and Q/A Debate	Moderated by Edenway SL team
12:55h	Closure (with presentation of the Visual Thinking picture being done during the webinar)	Ale Listen & Draws and Edenway SL Team

Table 1. Agenda organization of the Final Conference. (Source: CHESSE SETUP Consortium)

Finally, the Pilot experiences were allowed more time to present and in order to fit with the planned schedule, the Challenges and Q/A part were answered after every intervention and through the chat.

Additionally, as it can be seen in the Agenda, a service of online digital graphic interpretation was contracted for the Final Conference. The result is a full **Visual Thinking picture (Annex 4)** and a time lapse video of the conference and CHESSE SETUP project. This tool helps the audience to get back to what has been discussed and it was used as a wrap up of the event. The tool is also powerful for communication purposes and it is going to be disseminated post-conference through CHESSE SETUP communication channels, such as the website, social media accounts and post in BUILD UP or similar networks.

Link to all the Visual Thinking Materials in the CHESSE SETUP website [here](#).

Figure 4. Visual summary of the Final Conference of CHESSE SETUP
(Source: Ale Listens & Draws)

In conclusion, the final conference had 76 registrants (not including the direct partners of the Consortium), and finally 57 participants attended the event (42 via ZOOM and 15 via YouTube live-streaming). They came from different countries, being the top 5 Spain (41%), United Kingdom (11%), Netherlands (6%), Italy (6%) and Finland or Sweden (4%). Internationally, for example, they were participants from USA, Canada, Israel or Ghana.

Figure 5. Final Conference: Country statistics of the participants (Own source)

All the materials (Brochure, Video, Q/A collection, full recording of the conference and presentation – Link [here](#) to the sum up in our website with the materials included) were sent to the registrants along with a [satisfaction survey](#). To this day (28/09/2020), after 2 working-days of sending it, 8 responses have been received. Overall, all 8 expressed a very positive satisfaction with the event (63% very good, 38% excellent) and the sessions (63% excellent, 38% very good). Regarding the event length, the majority coincides that it was alright. Another question was asked in relation to the interest in CHESSETUP solution and, from now, the results seem promising:

- Knowing that CHESSETUP sets a precedent in terms of integrating renewable technologies (50%)
- Considering the implementation for the future after analysis (38%)
- Forwarding and dissemination the information of CHESSETUP (38%)
- Prescribing or recommending CHESSETUP solution for other projects (50%)
- Implementing or are in the process of starting the installation of CHESSETUP (25%)
- Interested in collaborating (13%)

The Consortium will be carrying on monitoring the survey and disseminating the solution, taking the relevant actions to respond to needs, comments and carry out the necessary exploitation.

One topic to mention is the collection of interest letters regarding CHESSE SETUP system, as mentioned in Deliverable 6.4. Market research and exploitation plan. The Consortium has received two more letters after the Final Conference (see Annex 3).

2.3 Specific workshop/sessions and webinars

Webinar 1. Best practices for retrofitting EU buildings

On June 20th 2018, the first online webinar organized by CHESSE SETUP was celebrated. As CHESSE SETUP was growing bigger, it was time for it to learn from its older siblings. We reviewed other experiences of buildings' retrofits to give you an idea of what to expect from CHESSE SETUP and to discuss the best practices for retrofitting European buildings.

A one-hour session was designed to remind the audience the main promises and advances of CHESSE SETUP and to introduce three other educative European experiences. THERMOS, OptEEemAL and TESSe2b EU projects shared and discussed the best practices they experienced to reduce their energy dependency and be part of the future. The session was complemented at the end by a half-hour interactive Q&A and debate about the topics.

The first webinar had 24 participants (7 speakers and 17 attendees) coming from different countries and different type of organizations (SMEs, Research centers and education institutions, international or national associations and public bodies).

Figure 6. Webinar 1: Country statistics of the participants (Own source)

Link to the Webinar 1 Report [here](#) and Presentation [here](#).

Webinar 2. An innovative approach to Thermal Energy Storage and Self-Sufficiency in Buildings

Webinar: An innovative approach to Thermal Energy Storage and Self-Sufficiency in Buildings

WHEN? 19 December 2019
11:00am-12:30pm (CET)

Organised by

With special collaboration from

Time (CET) AGENDA

11:00-11:05h	Welcome to the webinar
11:05-11:20h	CHESSE SETUP approach to Thermal Energy Storage and Self-Sufficiency in Buildings
11:20 - 11:35h	ReLATED approach
11:35 - 11:50h	SUNHORIZON approach
11:50 - 12:05h	HYBUILD approach
12:05 - 12:30h	Q/A and debate

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 680556.

On December 19th 2019, CHESSE SETUP project organized and hosted a public webinar called "An innovative approach to Thermal Energy Storage and Self-Sufficiency in Buildings".

This webinar allowed the attendees to learn about the CHESSE SETUP solution, results and its approach to Thermal Energy Storage and Self-sufficiency in

buildings. Then, ReLATED, SUNHORIZON and HYBUILD EU-projects, as guest speakers, presented their projects and approaches. At the end, a very interesting Q/A debate part was held.

In conclusion, the webinar evaluations were very good (67% excellent qualification) and it allowed the 28 participants (5 speakers and 23 attendees) to know more about the topic, and disseminate the projects around an audience coming from Europe (Spain, Germany, England, Italy, Netherlands, Albania, Poland...) as well as internationally, such as USA.

Figure 7. Webinar 2: Country statistics of the participants (Own source)

Link to the Webinar 2 Report [here](#) and Presentation [here](#).

Specific session: Feedback Contest

On June 2018, the project organized an Online Feedback Contest to contribute in order to improve and adapt the project. The winner received an attractive reward (Iberian ham). The participation was notorious and we received an enriching, exhaustive and documented feedback about CHESSE SETUP.

2.4 Local take-up events or one to one communication meetings

CHESSE SETUP meets ECOMESH

On October 2016, some of the CHESSE SETUP partners visited Ecomesh's factory located in Zaragoza (Spain). Ecomesh is the only Spanish company producing and commercializing second generation solar hybrid panels. The technology has been included in CHESSE SETUP project.

The partners first discovered the show room, where several prototypes of solar hybrid panels were exposed, from the first modules to the last generation ones. The main achievements of second-generation solar panels are the reduction of thermal losses in the front side of the panel, which means an increase of the thermal efficiency.

Ecomesh team explained the technical parameters of the panels and several possible configurations of hybrid solar panels with CHESSE SETUP were discussed.

EINSTEIN Project meeting

On December 2016, during the 2nd project meeting of the project held in Bilbao, all the partners of CHESSE SETUP met with Tecnalia team from EINSTEIN Project. The aim was to share insights about the two projects. Furthermore, the team visited EINSTEIN's pilot in the Bilbao's Manhattan.

Smart City Project MAtchUP meeting

On December 2017, Eurogrant organized a one-to-one meeting with the local MAtchUP Project partners from Dresden to present and discuss both projects. In total, 11 people were present in the meeting.

Conference call with Abracadabra project

On May 2018, Edenway hold a conference call with the dissemination team of the Abracadabra project to look for synergies between the two projects. CHESSE SETUP could be one of the Abracadabra pilots, and the methodology to gather data has been sent to the retrofitted CSU pilots (Sant Cugat and Lavola). In total, 4 people participated in the call.

Sant Cugat Quality Week

On November 2018, Sant Cugat del Vallès City Hall celebrated the Quality Week of the city. The Quality Week organized 24 different activities around sports and healthy attitudes as a driver and as a driving force to become a healthy community.

The team of Sant Cugat del Vallès City Hall working on CHESSE SETUP project organized and gave a seminar about the project and the pilot in the city sport center, which it is aiming to become a more energy-efficient and self-sufficient building. The audience consisted of 50 people, coming from different departments of the city's public body.

Educational Activity in the Ecobuilding of Lavola, pilot of CHESSE SETUP

On February 2020, Lavola organized an educational activity consisting in a visit to the pilot installations to 20 students from Rocavedra School (Torelló, Spain). The aim was to raise awareness among the young generations of the importance of energy efficiency and clean energy adaptation in the built environment, in order to fight climate change and meet the European climate targets.

3. Participation in third parties' events

The CHESSE SETUP partners have participated at conferences, meetings, seminars etc. both at local, national, EU level and also international to foster CHESSE SETUP visibility, exchange experiences with other similar projects and create interconnections with them, engage with stakeholders and raise awareness among the energy and building sector. The partners delivered presentations and publicized abstracts in these third parties' events. The goal was to boost the visibility of CHESSE SETUP, strengthen and broaden the relationship with the stakeholders' ecosystem.

Below there is a description of the most relevant events. Mention that Wansdrong partner had a very active role, therefore only some of them are described here and the complete list can be found in **Annex 1** of this deliverable (both, the presentation given and assistance/networking and also the audience and number of people attending are reported).

Smart City Expo World Congress 2016

On November 2016, in the first stage of the project, Barcelona Ecologia (LP) gave an introduction speech about CHESSE SETUP at the Smart City Expo World Congress in Barcelona. The project is closely related to the framework of the congress as its main objective is to provide a reliable and

replicable solution for building's self-sufficiency in the growing smart cities.

The partner explained to the visitors the project's root: the central question of lowering the energy consumption of the housing sector. From the two options, lowering demand, or raising efficiency, stemmed ideas of energy storage.

Barcelona Ecologia also detailed CHESSE SETUP outline, through each work package's objectives, and the further goals of this H2020 project.

CHESSE SETUP at 3rd conference on Smart Energy Systems and 4th Generation District Heating

On September 2017, the 3rd conference on Smart Energy Systems and 4th Generation District Heating was organized by Aalborg University in Copenhagen.

The aim of the conference was to present and discuss scientific findings and industrial experiences related to the subject of Smart Energy Systems based on renewable energy. The 3-year old conference is getting renowned, and this year 350 participants from 25 countries attended the event. In particular, around 50 people attended CHESSE SETUP presentation.

CHESSE SETUP was selected in the call for abstract, thanks to its contribution to the topics of Smart Energy System, and Future district heating production and systems. Leading partner Barcelona Ecologia introduced the project and its three pilot sites.

Smart City Expo World Congress 2017

On November 2017, all the partners participated in a two-hour session that was given to CHESSE SETUP Consortium to introduce the project's objectives and first achievements in the congress. Besides short presentations lead by the partners, there was time allocated for discussion, especially with projects sharing the same concerns as CHESSE SETUP. Around 50 people attended CHESSE SETUP activity.

Publication of abstract in Madrid NZEB Conference book

On November 2019, CHESSE SETUP abstract was selected to be published in the [conference's book](#) of this major Spanish event focusing on NZEB.

CHESSE SETUP in ICREN 2018

On April 2018, the City Council of Sant Cugat del Vallès represented CHESSE SETUP at the International Conference on Renewable Energy (ICREN) that was held in Barcelona to give a global overview of the latest progress towards a more sustainable future.

The speaker explained the objectives and functioning of the project, the partners involved, the system configuration and the monitoring and management system. He also ended up presenting the current state of advances of the different pilots in Corby, Manlleu and Sant Cugat. Access the presentation [here](#).

CHESSE SETUP in EU Sustainable Energy Week 2018

On June 2018, Wandsronk partner represented CHESSE SETUP in Brussels EUSEW event. The partner exposed CHESSE SETUP and Emporium Concept as a solution for long-term energy storage to an audience of 25 people attending the Energy Lab session.

CHESSE SETUP in HORIZON 2020 Energy Efficiency

On June 2018, Wandsronk partner presented CHESSE SETUP in the event organized by the French Focus Point of HORIZON 2020 in Paris. The topic was around energy efficiency and the speaker exposed CHESSE SETUP and Emporium Concept as a solution for energy efficiency in buildings in front of 21 attendees of other European funded projects.

CHESSE SETUP in Green Buildings Congress Innovation Challenge

On June 2018, Wandsronk partner also take the role to expose CHESSE SETUP project and system in the Green Buildings Congress Innovation Challenge celebrated in Amsterdam. The audience was of 60 people coming from the building and energy sector.

Solar auto-production roadmap by ProSumeProject

On October 2018, the final conference of the ProSumE project (Enabling Energy Prosumers Services) was celebrated in Valencia with the participation of Las Naves, València Clima i Energia, Climate-KIC, Universitat Politècnica de València, Universitat de València, AVAESSEN, IVACE and Greenpeace, among others.

It took place in a context of recent important changes in the Spanish legislation related to solar energy production, which have removed some legislative and administrative barriers and, as some of the speakers said, these changes have helped improving the acceptance and knowledge of this technology among citizens. Barcelona Ecology (LP), representing CHESSE SETUP project, participated in the session and the workshop with other stakeholder to define a solar auto-production roadmap.

You can find a summary of the conference [here](#), published by CHESSE SETUP in its website.

CHESSE SETUP in SBE 19 in Scilla

On May 2019, CHESSE SETUP was presented as a study case by Ajuntament de Sant Cugat in SBE 19 in Scilla (Italy). The objective of the event was focused on policies, programs and action plans targeted to improve the sustainability of the built environment.

“Energy savings in the company: The opportunity for photovoltaic self-consumption”

The workshop aroused much interest around the business and industrial people and it was attended by around 80 people. Self-consumption of photovoltaics was presented as a good opportunity to improve business competitiveness. A networking session was organized and also a guided tour of the installation that Manlleu company Lavola-Anthesis has in its eco-building, pilot of CHESSE SETUP. The system and the project were presented to the audience by Lavola team.

“Act for climate emergency: application of measures to mitigate your footprint” Workshops

On June 2019 and January 2020, the Catalan Office of Climate Change organized two workshops on which different actions were presented that may be brought to the attention of the organizations for reducing their direct energy consumption and also reducing GHG emissions and associated costs. Lavola Ecobuilding, pilot of CHESSE SETUP, was presented in both workshops as a case study, including the CHESSE SETUP project. Around 15-20 people coming from public administrations related to the energy, climate change fight and built environment attended the workshop.

“Heat Pump Water Heaters: A Challenging Future & Advanced Vapour Compression and/or sorption heat pumps with minimum compact thermal storage for DHW” Workshop and Exposition in the International Congress of Refrigeration

On August 2019, the partner Ulster University (CTS), attended and presented part of the work carried out regarding heat pumps research in the framework of H2020 funded CHESSE SETUP project in the 25th International Congress of Refrigeration held in Montreal (Canada).

ICR 2019
THE 25th IIR INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS OF REFRIGERATION
August 24-30 | Montréal, Québec, Canada

850 Participants	45 Countries represented	17 Keynote speakers	2 Plenary session: 2 speakers
9 Workshops	534 Oral presentations based on manuscript	72 Posters based on manuscript	10 Commission and working group meetings

CHESS SETUP in a BBC Radio Show

On September 2019, the eco homes and the earth Energy Bank systems in Corby Pilot, including reference to CHESS-SETUP, made an appearance in the [BBC Radio Northampton in the UK](#).

CleanTech Mission to Boston: CHESS SETUP in the Horizon 19 Conference

On September 2019, Wandsronk partner presented CHESS SETUP in the event [Horizon19 Conference and Pitch Arena](#) in Boston. The pitches were of 10 minutes in length and 5 minutes allocated for questions. 15 people in the conference and 50 to the pitching sessions were present during the partner’s presentation of CHESS SETUP and Emporium Concept - Zero-Emission Buildings. The system/concept was seen as a solution to act on clean energy and climate commitments in concert with the Paris Agreement, 2030 Sustainability Goals, We are Still In, and America’s Pledge. Horizon19 was seen as an excellent event and platform for transformational partnerships and networking.

CHESS SETUP in the 9th International Conference on economic development and social sustainability in Iran

On December 2019, Sant Cugat del Vallès partner, represented by engineer Victor Martinez del Rey, participated at the conference explaining the pilot of the city of the CHESS SETUP project. 75 people of all around the world but specially from Iran attended the Conference. They came from different backgrounds such as companies Research centers and education institutions, international or national associations and public bodies.

Utilising Modern Methods of Construction in large-scale development Event

On April 2020, Electric Corby partner participated in a half-day seminar organized by "New Communities Group" in London (UK) within the TCPA (Town & County Planning Association). Electric Corby presented the Corby pilot with the CHESSE SETUP system installed as an exemplar alongside presentation from United Kingdom Modern Methods of Construction build experts. The audience were mainly from local governments (municipalities).

An article about the case study was also included in the Practical Guide published within the [TCPA New Communities Guide for Local Authorities on Modern Methods of Construction \(UK\)](#).

4. Conclusions: Impact

The number of attendees (audience) related to the impact indicator/s established in the Communication and Dissemination Plan of CHESSE SETUP project (Deliverable 7.1) have been included throughout the document, as well as the people's evaluation (satisfaction) in the case of the Webinars and Final Conference event.

In the Plan (D7.1), a set of general Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for evaluating the progress and impact of the communication and dissemination activities was presented. In the case of the events (Clustering Activities, Local Events and One-to-one communication) the established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were aimed to monitor the number of people that attended the presentation, seminar or meetings about CHESSE SETUP project. The KPIs from the D7.1 were adapted, for this case, as follows:

- **Type of channel:** for communicate and disseminate the project.

Clustering Activities, Local Events and One-to-one meetings

- **General:** referring to the **input** indicators.

1. Number of events attended

Level 1. Organization of specific events for the project

- 10

Level 2. Third parties' events

- 120 (including face-to-face, virtual, mailing, calls, events).

2. Time spent on workshop/event organization

Level 1. Organization of specific events for the project

- 2-10 days on average for event

Level 2. Third parties' events

- 1-2 day on average for event

- **Echo:** referring to the **output** indicators which give the impact of the activity.

3. Number of people attending

- Indicated, when data was available, alongside this document both when exposing Level 1 and Level 2 events.

4. People's evaluation (satisfaction with the event)

- Indicated in the parts exposing the Webinars and Final Conference (own organized events)

5. Number of type/s of audience or stakeholders/target groups reached via the final journals (following the stakeholders and targets exposed in Figure 2- 7 types of stakeholders).

- 7 targeted groups

Annex 1. Other relevant communication and dissemination activities

In the Communication and Dissemination Plan of CHESSE SETUP (D7.1), other communication activities apart from clustering activities, one-to-one meetings, press releases, articles and graphical materials were presented through the creation and use of a website and social media channels for the project. All the communication and dissemination activities exposed in WP7 deliverables were published and dynamized through them.

The Website

The flagship of the consortium which can be accessed through the URL <https://www.chess-setup.net>. It contains all institutional information about the project and is intended to be used as the entry point of the different target audiences. The website acts as a communication and dissemination channel for the project's results and for the involvement of the project target groups.

On the website is published CHESSE SETUP's project information and status, news items, the abstracts, scientific articles, public deliverables, a timeline of CHESSE SETUP's Twitter account, the press releases, information about some of the clustering events in which CHESSE SETUP took part or organized. A "Frequently Asked Questions" (FAQ) heading has been edited, as well as a contact form in order to allow one-to-one communication. The website has been updated on a regular basis, providing the most relevant activities and articles possible.

In order to make the web attractive and user-friendly, the content/ distribution was designed to facilitate the answer to the fundamental questions about the project: What? Who? Why? When? How? This information was grouped in the main horizontal menu sections as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 8. CHESSE SETUP website design

The analysis of the website statistics in terms of number of visits provides an idea of the impact of online audiences through this media. The data were collected through the Visitor Analytics that incorporates the WIX software used to manage the website. From its publication in September 2016 to the last month of the project (Last retrieved: 28/09/2020) the website had a total of **4.351 visitors** with a time of **3 minutes on average spent per session**. In general, ever year the number of visitors has increased exponentially (Figure 10). The visitors by country are mainly, in this order, from Spain, UK, rest of Europe and USA.

Figure 9. World map showing in green the visitor's countries of CHESS SETUP website (Source: WIX)

Figure 10. Evolution of CHESS SETUP website visits (Source: WIX)

In particular, during the last phase of the project (May - September 2020), the number of **visits increased 56%** and the **number of unique visitors 37%**.

Social Media: Twitter

[CHESS SETUP Twitter account](#) is exploited on a weekly basis, publishing at least 2 tweets per week, as a content sharing platform and as a dissemination channel towards leading stakeholders in the building and energy sector with topics such as green buildings, energy efficiency, heat pumps, renewables, renovation wave, climate change initiatives, European Green Deal and cross-promotion of other H2020 EU-Funded Projects (see Sister Projects Initiative). Dedicated hashtags have been used in order to maximize visibility on the channel and the interesting topics.

Until September 2020 (Last retrieved: 28/09/2020), CHESS SETUP twitter account numbers are of **417 followers and 1090 tweets**.

Social Media: LinkedIn

CHESS SETUP LinkedIn company account is exploited on a weekly basis, publishing at least 1-2 posts per week, as a content sharing platform and as a dissemination channel like Twitter.

The page has **77 total followers** until today (Last retrieved: 28/09/2020). Additionally, the new analytic tool included recently in LinkedIn software allows to observe the impact from the last 12 months. In a nutshell, and from the last 12 months available (September 19 – August 20), May 2020 was the month that the account received a **greater number of visits** (25 in a desktop and 21 in mobile) (Figure 11). It was also on May 2020 when a **higher number of followers** were gained (11, increase of 266% over the previous month) (Figure 12). Finally, it is noteworthy to mention that in relation to **visitors' demographics**, the **top job project and functions** of the visitors are Community and Social Services (16%), Engineering (11%), Program and Project Management (11%) and Sales (11%) (Figure 13).

Figure 11. CHESSE SETUP LinkedIn visitor metrics (Sep 2019 - Aug 2020)

Figure 12. CHESSE SETUP LinkedIn follower metrics (Sep 2019 - Aug 2020)

Figure 13. CHESSE SETUP LinkedIn visitor demographics (Sep 2019 - Aug 2020)

Social Media: YouTube

In the last phase of the project, due to the action of LIVE streaming the Final Conference via YouTube, CHESSE SETUP also created a [channel](#) in this video platform and it will be uploaded there with the aim to disseminate the final results and exploitation of the system. The YouTube channel has only been created in July 2020 and only being used during September 2020 (last month of the project), for the purpose of streaming the Final Conference and publishing the Final Project Video. Until its uploading (18/09/2020), the Video has 25 views and the streamed final conference 100 views.

Sister Project Initiative

It is important to mention the "Sister Projects" initiative that started up in 2019. The initiative is related to the objective of interchange dissemination strategies and look for synergies with other projects. In the website, [a new section](#) was created to announce it and present the synergies done with other EU-funded projects. These projects are also focusing on seeking energy efficiency and self-sufficiency in buildings. CHESSE SETUP is in contact with them and added them to its stakeholders' database. The main aim is to cross-promote and disseminate the projects and actions together through our communication tools, especially social media channels such as tweets and retweets in Twitter and sharing posts in LinkedIn.

Although we are currently in contact with more funded projects and from time to time we cross-promote our actions via Twitter and LinkedIn, 5 EU-funded projects have officially accepted the communication collaboration opportunity and are added into our Sister Projects initiative. As follows:

- **ReLaTED:** RELaTED objective is to provide an innovative concept of decentralized Ultra-Low Temperature (ULT) network solution that can pave the way for expanding and modernizing existing district heating networks as well as introducing and establishing district heating in emerging EU markets.
- **HYBUILD:** HYBUILD aims at developing cost-effective and environmental-friendly solutions, while ensuring comfort conditions in residential buildings located in two different climates: Mediterranean climate where cooling is critical; and Continental climate where a stronger focus is put on heating demand. The project develops two innovative compact hybrid electrical/thermal storage systems for stand-alone and district connected buildings.
- **Sunhorizon:** The main objective of SunHorizon is to demonstrate up to TRL 7 innovative and reliable Heat Pump solutions (thermal compression, absorption, reversible) that acting properly coupled and managed with advanced solar panels (PV, Hybrid, thermal) can provide heating and cooling to residential and tertiary building with lower emissions, energy bills and fossil fuel dependency.

- **LowUP:** LowUP is developing and demonstrating three new efficient technologies i.e. one heating and one cooling system for office buildings, and one heat recovery system for industrial processes. The LowUP technologies are being demonstrated at four locations: two ACCIONA facilities in Sevilla and Madrid, an automotive factory and a retirement home.
- **InteGRIDy:** InteGRIDy integrates cutting-edge technologies, solutions and mechanisms in a scalable cross-functional framework of replicable solutions to connect existing energy networks with diverse stakeholders. A **pilot site** is the **Rambla del Celler sports center in Sant Cugat del Vallès city**, the same as CHESSE SETUP's pilot. InteGRIDy pilot will be collaborating with CHESSE SETUP team as it will **complement CHESSE SETUP system**, integrating to the control system an energy intensive equipment (dehumidification plant) and more energy production (photovoltaic with battery). The goal is to optimize the energy consumption of the building based on network signals. <http://www.integriddy.eu/content/starting-collaboration-sister-project-chess-setup>

Furthermore, it is interesting to acknowledge that the first 3 projects participated in the second webinar organized by CHESSE SETUP as guest speakers, and all of them were invited in the Final Conference.

Sister Projects

European projects focusing on seeking energy efficiency and self-sufficiency in buildings

CHESSE SETUP is related to other EU funded projects focusing on seeking energy efficiency and self-sufficiency in buildings. We cross-promote and disseminate our projects and actions together.

RELaTED

RELaTED objective is to provide an innovative concept of decentralized Ultra-Low Temperature (ULT) network solution that can pave the way for expanding and modernizing existing district heating networks as well as introducing and establishing district heating in emerging EU markets.

HYBUILD

HYBUILD aims at developing cost-effective and environmental-friendly solutions, while ensuring comfort conditions in residential buildings located in two different climates: Mediterranean climate where cooling is critical, and Continental climate where a stronger focus is put on heating demand. The project develops two innovative compact hybrid electrical/thermal storage systems for stand-alone and district connected buildings.

SUNHORIZON

The main objective of Sun-Horizon is to demonstrate up to TRL 7 innovative and reliable Heat Pump solutions (thermal compression, adsorption, reversible) that acting properly coupled and managed with advanced solar panels (PV, Hybrid, thermal) can provide heating and cooling to residential and tertiary building with lower emissions, energy bills and fossil fuel dependency.

LOWUP

LowUP will develop and demonstrate three new efficient technologies: one heating and one cooling system for office buildings, and one heat recovery system for industrial processes. The LowUP technologies will be demonstrated at four locations: two ACCIONA facilities in Sevilla and Madrid, an automotive factory and a retirement home.

InterGRIDy

InteGRIDy integrates cutting-edge technologies, solutions and mechanisms in a scalable cross-functional, framework of replicable solutions to connect existing energy networks with diverse stakeholders. A pilot site is the Rambla del Celler sports center in Sant Cugat city, the same as CHESSE SETUP's pilot. InteGRIDy pilot will be collaborating with CHESSE SETUP team as it will complement CHESSE SETUP system, integrating to the control system an energy intensive equipment (dehumidification plant) and more energy production (photovoltaic with battery). The goal is to optimize the energy consumption of the building based on network signals.

Annex 2. Full list of events and information by partner Wansdronk

Action/Event/Tool	Place (city)	Date	Status	Audience	Description	Link
Interreg North Sea Region (NSR) Brightfields	Billund	14/6/16	Completed	29	Grid parity and zero carbon micro-generation of renewable energy	www.mpiuk.com
Interreg North Sea Region (NSR)	Billund	15/6/16	Completed	26	Building Blocks for the Future, Design to Innovate (D2i)	www.northsearegion.eu www.dzi.dk www.sdu.dk
Mix & Match	Amsterdam	20/6/16	Completed	15	Re-use of products and materials	www.kvk.nl
Thermo Chemical Material (TCM)	Utrecht	21/6/16	Completed	2	Storage technologies integration	www.duurzaam.hu.nl
Advanced Metropolitan Solutions (AMS)	Amsterdam	23/6/16	Completed	23	Research and Valorisation Programme	www.ams-institute.org
Knowledge Innovation Community InnoEnergy	Terrassa	5/7/16	Completed	2	Energy storage	www.kic-innoenergy.com/office/iberia/
VNDelta Warmtenetwerk	Antwerpen	12/7/16	Completed	30	Flemish-Dutch Delta (VNDelta) Heat Network	www.vndelta.eu
Platform Nul-op-de-Meter (NOM) Nieuwbouw	Rosmalen	21/7/16	Completed	10	Platform Zero on the Meter New Built	www.kmidb.nl www.kwartiermakersindebouw.nl
COST Action TU1205	Warszawska	8/9/16	Completed	95	Building Integration of Solar Thermal Systems (BISTS)	www.cost.eu/COST_Actions/tud/TU1205 www.tu1205-bists.eu

CHES-SETUP Press Release	Amsterdam (Mail)	28/9/16	Completed	10	Press Release. Project Leaflet. Website Link	www.chess-setup.net
Vakbeurs Energie 2016	s Hertogenbosch	6/10/16	Completed	4	Energy Exhibition 2016	www.energievakbeurs.nl
COST Action TU1303	Newcastle	26/10/16	Completed	16	Sustainability and Efficiency New Structural Textile Materials and Designs	www.novelstructuralskins.eu www.costtu1303.eu
Interreg North Sea Region (NSR) Brightfields	Amsterdam	9/11/16	Completed	10	Grid parity and zero carbon micro-generation of renewable energy	www.mpiuk.com
Smart Cities and Communities (SCC)	Brussel	22/11/16	Completed	13	Smart Cities, Sustainable Districts and Built Environment (SDBE)	www.eu-smartcities.eu
Interreg Vlaanderen-Nederland VL-NL Demi More	Westerlo	24/11/16	Completed	8	Demonstration of Energy efficiency by Measurement and Innovation	www.grensregio.eu
Platform Nul-op-de-Meter (NOM) Nieuwbouw	s Hertogenbosch	9/12/16	Completed	22	Platform Zero on the Meter New Built	www.kmidb.nl www.kwartiermakersindebouw.nl
Nationale Energiecommissie, Energiedialoog	Amsterdam	12/1/17	Completed	4	National Energy Commission, The National Energy Dialogue	www.energiecommissie.nl
Bouwbeurs 2017, Material Xperience 2017	Utrecht	8/2/17	Completed	12	Construction Exhibition, Material Xperience	www.bouwbeurs.nl www.materia.nl www.materialexplorer.com
COST Action TU1303	Eindhoven	8/3/17	Completed	64	Sustainability and Efficiency New Structural Textile Materials and Designs	www.novelstructuralskins.eu www.costtu1303.eu
Building Holland 2017,	Amsterdam	12/4/17	Completed	22	Enterprise Europe Network	www.een.ec.europa.eu

Building Europe 2017					(EEN), Building Europe	www.buildingholland.nl/building-europe
Maatschappelijk Verantwoord Innoveren, Energie	Utrecht	6/6/17	Completed	4	Socially Responsible Innovation, Energy	www.tki-urbanenergy.nl
Road2GermanyXL	Zwolle	8/6/17	Completed	19	Implementation Renewable Energy System & Storage	www.kvk.nl
East Africa Business Dialogue (EABD)	s Gravenhage	15/6/17	Completed	10	Cooling System Research & Development	www.rvo.nl
Smart Cities and Communities	Brussel	20/6/17	Completed	10	Smart Cities, Sustainable Districts and Built Environment (SDBE)	www.eu-smartcities.eu
Horizon 2020 NRW, Successful R&I in Europe	Düsseldorf	15/3/18	Completed	55	Nanotechnology, Materials and Manufacturing (NMM), Energy	www.horizon2020.zenit.de
C-Energy 2020, Horizon 2020 Energy Efficiency	Manchester (Web)	26/4/18	Completed	16	Smart and Clean Energy for Consumers	www.euenergyfocus.co.uk
The Future of Building 2018	Wien (Web)	8/5/18	Completed	39	Sustainable and green building	www.wko.at/service/veranstaltungen.html
EU Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) 2018	Brussel	5/6/18	Completed	25	Networking Village, Energy Lab	www.eusew.eu
Key Enabling Technologies in Horizon 2020	Mainz	7/6/18	Completed	51	Energy efficiency in Buildings (PPP EeB)	www.kets2019.b2match.io
International Research Activities by SME (IraSME)	Berlin (Mail)	7/6/18	Completed	2	Collective Research Network (CORNET) Innovation Day	www.ira-sme.net/events/partnering-event-berlin-2018/
International Agency for	Groningen (Mail)	10/6/18	Completed	5	41st International Conference	www.iaee2018.com

Energy Economics (IAEE)						
COST Action CA16114	Koper (Mail)	13/6/18	Completed	124	Rethinking Sustainability Towards a Regenerative Economy (RESTORE)	www.eurestore.eu
International Business Festival IBF 2018	Liverpool	14/6/18	Completed	31	Global Renewable Energy Supply Chain Conference	www.internationalbusinessfestival.com
Horizon 2020 Energy Efficiency	Paris	21/6/18	Completed	21	Buildings (EE & EeB)	www.horizon2020.gouv.fr
Smart Cities and Communities (SCC)	Sofia	27/6/18	Completed	10	Smart Cities, Sustainable Districts and Built Environment (SDBE)	www.eu-smartcities.eu
World of Walas, Speedmeeting World of Walas	Heerlen	19/7/18	Completed	13	Energy storage, Carbon6 Heerlen and Phoenix Hochofenwerk Dortmund	www.worldofwalas.com/official-opening-carbonblue/
Green Buildings Conference 2018	Amsterdam	13/9/18	Completed	60	Innovation Challenge	www.cfp.nl/en/2018/05/24/green-buildings-innovation-challenge/
BY&FOR CITIZENS 2018	Valladolid (Mail)	20/9/18	Completed	7	European Conference on Smart, Sustainable and Resilient Cities	www.byforcitizens.com
FOR ARCH 2018	Praha (Mail)	21/9/18	Completed	6	International Brokerage Event	www.forarch2018.talkb2b.net
Energy4u 2018	Karlsruhe	27/9/18	Completed	20	Connect Ideas2Business	www.connectideas2business.org
Energy Info Days	Brussel	5/10/18	Completed	122	Energy Systems and Smart Cities & Communities	www.ec.europa.eu www.energycall2019.b2match.io
Renewable Energy &	Barcelona (Mail)	6/10/18	Completed	2	Academic Program	www.renewableenergy.euros

Emerging Technologies						cicon.com
Startupbootcamp, Smart Cities and Communities	Amsterdam	18/10/18	Completed	8	Smart City Experience (SCE)	www.eu-smartcities.eu/events/smart-city-experience
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Helmond	10/10/18	Completed	17	Kick-off Meeting	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Amsterdam	25/10/18	Completed	16	Catch Up Smart City Expo World Congress	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Amsterdam	25/10/18	Completed	13	Briefing Meeting	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Barcelona	11/11/18	Completed	15	Meet & Greet Reception	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Sant Cugat	12/11/18	Completed	52	Shaping the Future by Challenging Today Business Event	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Sant Cugat	12/11/18	Completed	20	Eurofitness Sant Cugat, Swimming Pool Pilot Visit	www.chess-setup.net
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Barcelona	13/11/18	Completed	51	Dutch Pavilion (Holland Paviljoen)	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Barcelona	14/11/18	Completed	45	Resilience Workshop Climate & Energy	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC)	Barcelona	13/11/18	Completed	31	Exhibition & Conference	www.smartcityexpo.com
Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC)	Barcelona	13/11/18	Completed	122	Smart City Brokerage Event	www.smartcity2018.b2match.io
Smart Cities and Communities (SCC)	Barcelona	14/11/18	Completed	6	Business Models, Finance and Procurement (BMFP)	www.eu-smartcities.eu
High-tech Sustainable	Brussel (Mail)	14/11/18	Completed	1	European Construction	www.ectp.org/news-

Built Environment					Technology Platform (ECTP) Conference	events/events/
Africa New Energy (ANE)	Capetown (Mail)	26/11/18	Completed	2	New Energy Update	www.events.newenergyupdate.com/africa/
COST Action TU1403	Luzern (Mail)	26/11/18	Completed	93	Adaptive Facades Network	www.tu1403.eu
Build & Connect 2018	Strasbourg (Mail)	28/11/18	Completed	2	Pioneering Technologies and Practices in the Sustainable Building	www.buildandconnect.eu
Netherlands Smart City Expo (NLSCE)	Eindhoven	7/1/19	Completed	38	Return Day	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Smart Cities South Korea	s Gravenhage	15/1/19	Completed	22	Urban Regeneration	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Interreg North Sea Region (NSR)	s Gravenhage	16/1/19	Completed	99	Interwork Event	www.northsearegion.eu
China Mission	Rotterdam	21/1/19	Completed	9	40 Years of Sister City Relations Rotterdam Shanghai	www.rotterdampartners.nl
Brainport Smart District (BSD)	Helmond	24/1/19	Completed	17	Business Challenge	www.brainportsmartdistrict.nl
DutchChain, Odyssey Hackaton	s Hertogenbosch	4/2/19	Completed	27	Tech Deep Dive	www.odyssey.org
DutchChain, Odyssey Hackaton	Amsterdam	5/2/19	Completed	40	Track Deep Dive, Nature 2.0	www.odyssey.org
DutchChain, Odyssey Hackaton	Rotterdam	7/2/19	Completed	25	Track Deep Dive, Digital Nations Infrastrucuture	www.odyssey.org
DutchChain, Odyssey Hackaton	Amsterdam	7/2/19	Completed	25	Track Deep Dive, Fossil Free Future	www.odyssey.org

DutchChain, Odyssey Hackaton	s Gravenhage	8/2/19	Completed	20	Track Deep Dive, 21st Century Digital Citizenship, Scaling Ecosystems	www.odyssey.org
Bauz! 2019	Wien	14/2/19	Completed	36	Vienna Congress on Sustainable Building	www.bauz.at
World Sustainable Energy Days (WSED) 2019	Wels (Mail)	27/2/19	Completed	3	Innovation Workshops Energy and Buildings	www.wsed.at
Futurebuild 2019	London	6/3/19	Completed	59	Futurebuild Matchmaking	www.futurebuild.co.uk
Green Build Europe 2019	Amsterdam (Mail)	19/3/19	Completed	7	Human X Nature	www.greenbuild.usgbc.org/europe
Smart City Summit & Expo (SCSE) 2019	Taipei (Mail)	26/3/19	Completed	3	Sub-Expo Intelligent Building Expo (IBE)	www.smartcity.org.tw
COST Action CA18136	Brussels	1/4/19	Completed	63	European Forum for Advanced Practices (EFAP)	www.cost.eu/actions/CA18136/
Innovation Cooperation Summit	Eindhoven	4/4/19	Completed	19	China (Nanjing) - the Netherlands (Eindhoven)	www.4cnconsult.com
Dutch National Research Agenda	Utrecht	15/4/19	Completed	72	Energy Transition Route	www.nera.nl/nwa-energy-transition-route/
Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy (EE&RE)	Sofia (Mail)	16/4/19	Completed	2	Smart Cities	www.viaexpo.com/en/pages/ee-re-exhibition
Smart Cities New York (SCNY)	Rotterdam	18/4/19	Completed	15	Dutch Mission, Kick-off Meeting	www.smartcitiesny.com
LIFE Info Day 2019	Brussel	30/4/19	Completed	54	EU LIFE Information and Networking Day	www.eulife2019.b2match.io
Smart Cities New York (SCNY)	New York (Mail)	13/5/19	Completed	16	State of New York Associations and Research	www.smartcitiesny.com

					Institutes	
Smart Cities and Communities (SCC)	Brussel (Mail)	16/5/19	Completed	2	Business Models, Finance and Procurement (BMFP)	www.eu-smartcities.eu
The Future of Building 2019	Wien (Mail)	4/6/19	Completed	70	Congress, B2B Meetings and Workshops	www.wko.at/service/veranstaltungen
PROVADA 2019	Amsterdam	6/6/19	Completed	10	Smart Cities, Blockchain in Real Estate	www.provada.nl
China Mission	Shanghai (Mail)	11/6/19	Completed	9	40 Years of Sister City Relations Rotterdam Shanghai	www.rotterdampartners.nl
CHARGE 2019	Utrecht	13/6/19	Completed	16	Energy Transition & Sustainability	www.clicknl.nl/charge/
EU Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) 2019	Brussel (Mail)	18/6/19	Completed	4	Shaping Europe's EnergyFuture	www.eusew.eu
Campus Amsterdam Metropolitan Conference	Amsterdam	20/6/19	Completed	16	Design Sprint on Innovation District Marine Area	www.wemakethe.city
Blockchain Expo Europe 2019	Amsterdam	20/6/19	Completed	19	AI & Big Data, Cyber Security & Cloud, IoT Tech	www.blockchain-expo.com
E2tech4Cities and Brussels Exporters Day 2019	Brussel (Mail)	20/6/19	Completed	6	Energy & Efficiency Technologies for Cities	www.e2tech4cities19expo.b2match.io
ASEAN Business Forum 2019	s Gravenhage	24/6/19	Completed	10	Partnerships for Sustainability	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Doing Business in the Gulf Region	Amsterdam	2/7/19	Completed	11	Energy, Food, Water	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Natural Gas Free WG Site	Amsterdam	15/7/19	Completed	12	Energy Transition	www.ketelhuiswg.nl
Smart Connected World CELTIC-NEXT	London	20/8/19	Completed	40	CELTIC Innovate UK Summer Briefing	www.celticnext.eu/event

Information Technology European Advancement	Amsterdam	3/9/19	Completed	150	ITEA Project Outline (PO) Days	www.itea3.org/podays2019/po-days-2019
EUREKA Stakeholder Conference (ESC) 2019	Amsterdam	5/9/19	Completed	24	Creating Ecosystems for Innovation	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Cleantech Mission to Boston	s Gravenhage	10/9/19	Completed	12	Pitch You!	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Green Buildings Congress 2019	Bussum (Mail)	12/9/19	Completed	1	Innovation Challenge	www.cfp.nl/en/2019/03/29/cfp-innovation-day/
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Amsterdam (Mail)	15/9/19	Completed	246	Energy Systems & Sustainable Buildings	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Cambridge	17/9/19	Completed	3	New England Opportunities	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Cambridge	17/9/19	Completed	4	MIT Senseable City Lab	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Cambridge	17/9/19	Completed	5	MIT Materials Research Lab (MRL)	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston	17/9/19	Completed	7	Networking Reception	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston	18/9/19	Completed	10	Site Visit Suffolk Downs Project	www.showcase.cleantechscandinavia.com/boston/
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Somerville	18/9/19	Completed	7	Cleantech Showcase	www.showcase.cleantechscandinavia.com/boston/
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Somerville	18/9/19	Completed	1	Cleantech Showcase, Session HEET's GeoMicroDistrict Project	www.showcase.cleantechscandinavia.com/boston/
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Somerville	18/9/19	Completed	100	Cleantech Showcase, Company Presentations	www.showcase.cleantechscandinavia.com/boston/
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston	19/9/19	Completed	15	Horizon19, Conference	www.horizon19.org

Boston						
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston	19/9/19	Completed	50	Horizon19, Pitch Arena	www.horizon19.org
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston	20/9/19	Completed	2	Site Visit Clippership Wharf Project	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston	20/9/19	Completed	3	Site Visit Bulfinch Crossing Project	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston	20/9/19	Completed	6	Development and Planning Agencies	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Amsterdam (Mail)	29/9/19	Completed	49	Energy Systems & Sustainable Buildings	www.aanmelder.nl/cleantechboston
COST Action CA18136	Madrid	11/10/19	Completed	82	European Forum for Advanced Practices (EFAP)	www.cost.eu/actions/CA18136/
Prefabricated Building PBCTE 2019	Changsha (Mail)	13/10/19	Completed	2	Prefabricated Building and Construction Technology Expo	www.higbe.org
Growing beyond the border	Amsterdam	17/10/19	Completed	1	Sustainable and Affordable Energy for Everyone	www.atradius.nl
China's Future Society	Amsterdam	19/10/19	Completed	21	Conference & Matchmaking	www.3ntry.nl
Design Research & Innovation Festival (DRIVE)	Eindhoven (Mail)	24/10/19	Completed	1	Energy Transition & Sustainability	www.click.nl/drive/
100% Renewable Heating & Cooling	Helsinki (Mail)	28/10/19	Completed	1	100% Renewable Heating & Cooling for a Sustainable Future	www.rhc-platform.org/100-rhc-event/
EBRD Green Cities	s Gravenhage	30/10/19	Completed	7	Green Cities Action Plan (GCAP)	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Extinction Rebellion	Amsterdam	3/11/19	Completed	2	Political Strategy & Change	www.extinctionrebellion.nl

Netherlands XRNL						
Cumulus Park	Amsterdam	21/11/19	Completed	5	Collaborative Innovation District	www.cumuluspark.com
FIBREE	Amsterdam	21/11/19	Completed	3	Orchestration of Building Data	www.fibree.org
Renewable Energy Morocco	s Gravenhage	27/11/19	Completed	7	Business Opportunities for Morocco's Renewable Energy Sector	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Sustainable Building Sweden	s Gravenhage	5/12/19	Completed	10	Nordbygg Expo	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Business Week North-America	Nieuwegein	9/12/19	Completed	17	Renewable Energy & Storage Canada, Mexico, United States	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Business Week North-America	Rotterdam	12/12/19	Completed	12	Renewable Energy & Storage Canada, Mexico, United States	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Creative Holland, Canton Fair	Amsterdam	18/12/19	Completed	6	Linking Design and Industry Creating Value for Business	www.creativeholland.com
Abu Dhabi Sustainability Week (ADSW)	Abu Dhabi (mail)	11/1/20	Completed	3	World Future Energy Summit (WFES)	www.abudhabisustainabilityweek.com
Business in Turkey	s Gravenhage	14/1/20	Completed	3	Sustainable an Renewable Energy	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
Klimahouse 2020	Bolzano (mail)	22/1/20	Completed	6	Future Hub	www.fierabolzano.it/klimahouse/
Ambassadors Conference	s Gravenhage	29/1/20	Completed	2	Olympic Summer Games 2024 Paris	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
SOLIDEO	Amsterdam	30/1/20	Completed	3	Olympic Summer Games 2024 Paris	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/

Sustainable Building Sweden	Rotterdam	4/2/20	Completed	11	Nordic Business Day	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/
DutchChain, Odyssey Hackaton	s Gravenhage	5/2/20	Completed	12	Connect 2020	www.odyssey.org
World Sustainable Energy Days (WSED) 2020	Wels (Mail)	4/3/20	Completed	2	Innovation Workshops Energy and Buildings	www.wsed.at
Mission-Driven Research Development Innovation	Utrecht	5/3/20	Completed	27	Natural gas-free renovation packages	www.tki-urbanenergy.nl
COST Action CA18136	Utrecht	13/3/20	Completed	12	European Forum for Advanced Practices (EFAP)	www.cost.eu/actions/CA18136/
Circular City Week	New York (mail)	16/3/20	Completed	2	Built environment city planning and architecture	www.circularcityweek.com
Cleantech Mission to Boston	Boston (mail)	22/3/20	Completed	3	Energy Storage & Sustainable Buildings	www.rvo.nl/actueel/evenementen/

Table 2. Full list of events and information by partner Wansdronk

Annex 3. Letters of interest

D. Pere Gutierrez Alemany, en calidad de coordinador de la Compañía Energética VILAWATT con CIF: 38066585K muestra su interés en los resultados y conclusiones que se puedan extraer de la instalación que combina paneles solares híbridos (PV-T), acumulación térmica estacional y bomba de calor en los pilotos diseñados bajo el proyecto europeo CHESSE SETUP.

Dicho proyecto marca un precedente en cuanto a la integración de tecnologías renovables e instalaciones eficientes, permitiendo conseguir importantes coberturas solares (tanto eléctricas como térmicas) en diferentes tipos de edificios.

Por ello, en base a los resultados obtenidos, se analizará la viabilidad para su implementación en proyectos que promueva la Compañía Energética VILAWATT.

En Viladecans, a la fecha de la firma electrónica

Coordinador Compañía Energética VILAWATT

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Vilawatt Energy Company (Viladecans, Spain) shows interest in CHESSE SETUP system and they will analyse the viability of implementation in projects which the company promotes.

D. *Jordi Mazón Bueso*, en calidad de Presidente del Consejo Ejecutivo del Consorcio Vilawatt y *Teniente de Alcalde de Transición Ecológica del Ayuntamiento de Viladecans* con CIF: 52209182X muestra su interés en los resultados y conclusiones que se puedan extraer de la instalación que combina paneles solares híbridos (PV-T), acumulación térmica estacional y bomba de calor en los pilotos diseñados bajo el proyecto europeo CHESSE SETUP.

Dicho proyecto marca un precedente en cuanto a la integración de tecnologías renovables e instalaciones eficientes, permitiendo conseguir importantes coberturas solares (tanto eléctricas como térmicas) en diferentes tipos de edificios.

Por ello, en base a los resultados obtenidos, se analizará la viabilidad para su implementación en proyectos que promueva la Compañía Energética VILAWATT.

En Viladecans, a la fecha de la firma electrónica

Presidente del Consejo Ejecutivo del Consorcio Vilawatt i *Teniente de Alcalde de Transición Ecológica del Ayuntamiento de Viladecans*

**TCAT P Jordi
Mazón Bueso -
DNI
52209182X** Firmado digitalmente
por TCAT P Jordi
Mazón Bueso - DNI
52209182X
Fecha: 2020.09.22
14:46:23 +02'00'

Jordi Mazón

Vilawatt Energy Company (Viladecans, Spain) and Viladecans City Council show interest in CHESSE SETUP system and they will analyse the viability of implementation in projects which the company promotes in the city of Viladecans for energy transition.

Annex 4. Visual Thinking summary of CHESS SETUP (Final Conference)

FINAL CONFERENCE

CHESS

SET UP

18.09.2020

WELCOME AND OPENING

CLIMATE NEUTRAL
2050

BUILDING EFFICIENCY

IMPROVE GLOBAL ENVIRONMENTAL STANDARDS

2016-2020

DECARBONISING THE ENERGY SECTOR

INVEST IN ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY TECH.

CHES-SETUP

SELF SUFFICIENCY BUILDING

HORIZON 2020-EU PROJECT

LUCÍA GLEZ.
EDENWAY

CHES-SETUP • FINAL CONFERENCE • 18.09.20

CHESS SETUP: AN OVERVIEW

- NEW HEATING SOLUTIONS
- COMPATIBILITY WITH OTHER SYSTEMS
- TEST + MONITOR THE SYSTEM
- DEVELOP BUSINESS MODEL
- REDUCE ELECTRICITY DEMAND
- REDUCE INVESTMENT COSTS

10 ORGANISATIONS

EASY TO ADAPT FOR ALL BUILDINGS

ENERGY CONSUMED IN THE EU 40%

CO2 EMISSIONS IN THE EU 36%

WE SHOULD GO TO NZEB

CORBY (UK)

MANLEU (SP)

SANT CUGAT (SP)

TESTED IN DIFFERENT CLIMATES

RENE WANDRONK WANDRONK ARCH.

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ADVANCES IN HEAT PUMP IMPLEMENTATION

NEW HEAT PUMPS FOR HOUSING

CHALLENGES

CONCLUSIONS
ALIGNMENT OF A
NEW PUMP
WITH WIDE RANGING
CLIMATE
DEMAND

CLIMATE CHALLENGE

What is the maximum capacity deliverable from a wide speed unit?

EXTENS

NEAR → INSTANTANEOUS HOT WATER
What can it deliver from an start/off state?

COLD WINTER
TO HOT SUMMER

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PILOT EXPERIENCE: LAVOLA

LAVOLA OFFICES

PHOTOVOLTAIC PANNELS

NO THERMAL ENERGY IS WASTED

WE AVOIDED THE WASTE ENERGY IN SUMMER

SUPPLUS TO ELECTRIC GRID

AIR SOURCE HEAT PUMP

THERMAL STORAGE

BUFFER TANK

CRISTINA BAYÉS
LA VOLA ANTHESIS

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PILOT EXPERIENCE: ST. CUGAT

! We did not have ER sources

! We reduced extremely the energy bill

! 54% EXPECTED TO COVER THE NEEDS

HYBRID PANELS

SPORT CENTRE

OF POOLS + SPORT AREA

8 COUNTRIES

E.V into GRIDY PROJECT

NEXT

CONTINUITY TO OUR PROJECT

ADMIN

THREE POOLS

HEAT PUMP

BOILER

! HEATING NEEDS all Reached

! CONSTRUCTION PROBLEMS
! ESTIMATED VALUES but not REAL (due to covid)
! ELECTRICITY DEMAND not 100% reached
! We need 1 year more to reach the results

GERARD RIBA
AJT. SAINT CUGAT

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PILOT EXPERIENCE: CORBY

Difficult to have stable data

in someone's control

SOLAR PV PANNELS

SEASONAL HEAT STORAGE IS KEY PART TO ACHIEVE ENERGY POSITIVE

HEAT PUMP

WE MANAGED TO SET IT UP WITH SIMPLE + EFFECTIVE TECHNOLOGY

SOLAR ENERGY STORAGE

AN ATTRACTIVE BUSINESS MODEL

NICK BOLTON
CORBY PROJECT

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CAPITALIZATION: CONTROL AND MONITORING

JORDI FERRER
WATTIA INNOVA

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CAPITALIZATION: SIMULATION SOFTWARE

SERGIO SÁNCHEZ
 URBAN ECOLOGY AGENCY BCN

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CAPITALIZATION: ESCO

ENERGY SERVICES

⚡⚡⚡

MOST USED

ENERGY MANAGEMENT

MAINTENANCE

FULL WARRANTY REPAIR

HEATING ELECTRICITY

IMPROVEMENT WORKS AND RENEWAL

A DIFFERENT TYPE OF CONTRACTS

OPTIONS TO CHOOSE

WHOLE PACKAGE

CHOOSE AS YOU WANT

JOSEP MITATS
VEOLIA

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CAPITALIZATION: TRANSFERABILITY

PROJECTS IN SPAIN

We include CHES
Technology in
TENDER
PROPOSALS

ARPA

BRITISH
SCHOOL

ARANDA
DE DUERO

QUORON

BARBASTRO
HOSPITAL

UNIVERSITY
OF
ZARAGOZA

EMBO
BUSINESS
CENTRE

PRISON

ALEJANDRO del AMO
ABORA SOLAR

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